

Study of the evolution of the ethyl ester content of extra virgin olive oil after one year of storage and its impact on the quality of the oil

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Abstract

This study was carried out on 86 olive oil samples from the 2016 olive growing season, in three Moroccan regions; eastern region, central region and northern region, by analyzing the free acidity by titrimetric test (ISO 660) and the ethyl ester content by gas chromatography method 3 grams (COI / T.20 / DOC N ° 31 November). The samples were stored under special conditions and the study took place over two periods 6 and 12 months of storage. Taking into account the acidity analysis, the results obtained showed no change after 6 months of storage. We conclude that 17.44% of the samples degrade passing from the extra virgin category to a virgin category. For the ethyl ester content, 4.6% of the samples were degraded after 6 months of storage and 29.06% were degraded after one year of storage. In addition, we observed that the growing region of olive trees has an impact on the free acidity and the ethyl ester content of olive oil. For this criterion, we observed that in the central region of Morocco, the olive oil samples are the least degraded compared to other regions. Thus, concerning the content of ethyl esters, 13% of the samples come from the central region, 37% from the eastern region and 39% from the northern region. On the other hand, for the analysis of the acidity, 8% of the samples come from the center, 30% of the samples come from the oriental and 17.39% of the samples come from the north. So we can conclude that for the conservation of extra virgin olive oil, the olive trees of the central region of Morocco can benefit from a good storage while retaining their high nutritional quality proven by the analysis of acidity and the content of ethyl esters.

Key words: *quality, free acidity, ethyl ester, conservation, region.*

INTRODUCTION:

Olive oil is a biological product whose history goes back to antiquity. It was used as medicine and staple food by the whole Mediterranean population (Bejaoui et al., 2018). Outside the Mediterranean, countries where the olive oil consumption has always been rare, especially the United States, have begun in recent years to increase the demand for olive oil, representing 9% of world consumption (Costa et al., 2017). In addition, nutritionists are increasingly inclined to propose the Mediterranean diet as a healthy way against the dietary habits of modern life, rich in protein saturated fat, while olive oil offers a variety of unsaturated fatty acids including oleic acid and polyphenols (Bejaoui et al., 2018; Costa et al., 2017). In Morocco, olive growing is considered as a central socio-economic sector (Ater et al., 2015), since it is the main fruiting species in rapid extension, which plays a crucial role in agricultural development and especially in the framework of the Green Morocco Plan, where an olive orchard extension areas is planned to reach 1.2 million hectares and olive production of 2.5 million tonnes by 2020 (Ater et al., 2015). These orchards are scattered over different Moroccan regions where we found; the central region (Fez-Meknes), northern region (Tangier-Tétouan- Al Hoceima), Orientale region, and the southern provinces, whose predominant variety is Moroccan picholine that adapts well to the soil and climatic conditions of the whole country and has typical characteristics of double aptitude variety. The produced olives are used for all confectionery types: broken green olives with olives ripe black, having yield oil average (Meftah et al., 2014). Due to the well-known features and benefits of health (Fortini et al., 2015), extra virgin olive oil has become a target for illegal

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handling and fraud (Costa et al., 2017) which has attracted increasing interest from the scientific community in research that has been a subject of a regulation series which set specific parameters in order to guarantee oil authenticity and quality, and therefore consequently consumer safety (Costa et al., 2017). In this context, several studies have been made on olive oil characterization and confirmed the correlation between sensory analysis and alkyl esters amount (Bejaoui et al., 2018; Gomez et al., 2016 ; Biderman et al., 2008) specifically ethyl esters as new extra virgin olive oil evaluation parameter (Grompone et al., 2016), This concept represents a challenge that will enrich the informative data on this subject and the decision adopted by the IOC and the EU to reduce progressively ethyl esters content limit in extra virgin olive oils. All these data led us to investigate the impact of storage of an extra virgin olive oil by studying the ethyl esters content and the analysis of acidity during a long period on the quality of the oil. The method of preservation of the oil is very important in determining the quality of the oil which is sought after for all its organoleptic and nutritional characteristics which are beneficial for a better effect on human health.

MATERIEL AND METHODS:

Sampling:

86 olive oil samples come from Moroccan picholine variety from different cities in three Moroccan regions: Central Region (Fès-Meknès, region), Eastern and Northern Region (Tangier-Tetouan-Al Hoceima) ; from the 2015/2016 olive growing season, which was extracted by a two-phase crushing system.

Table 1: Samples distribution of olive oil according to their culture region

Region	Eastern region	Central region	Northern region
Number of samples	27	36	23

The olive oil samples were preserved in 150 ml clean, dry brown glass bottles, crimped with plastic caps and at a temperature that varies between 22 and 30 ° C, in order to avoid auto-oxidation phenomenon which depends on several factors, such as; free fatty acids, presence of metal traces and water, packaging used, ambient temperature, atmosphere oxygen and daylight exposure for clear packs.

Experimental protocol

- *Free acidity:*

The acidity is determined according to the method (ISO 660), intended for animal and vegetable fats, which consists of a titrimetric test in which the sample is solubilized in a mixture (50% / 50%); diethyl ether / ethanol with an ethanolic solution of potassium hydroxide (0.1 N), in presence of phenolphthalein as color indicator. Results are expressed in% (m / m) of oleic acid equivalent (ISO, 2009).

- *Ethyl ester:*

The ethyl ester content was determined by 3 gram method (COI / T.20 / Doc No. 31 November 2012), which consists in adding an appropriate quantity (1 ml) of internal standard (methyl heptadecanoate) to the sample to be analyzed, which will be purified and fractionated by chromatography on column of silica gel hydrated with hexane (3 grams of deactivated silica with 2% distilled water), the eluted fraction will subsequently be recovered and evaporated to dryness at room temperature. Using a rota-vapor and analyzed by capillary column gas chromatography (vector gas: nitrogen, length: 12 m, diameter: 0.25, thickness: 0.25 µm) (COI, 2012; Squeo et al., 2017).

RESULT:

Free acidity

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- 1st analysis step:

All samples are ext Fig 1: Free acidity percentage in T₀ (0 month conservation)

- 2nd analysis step

Fig 2: Free acidity percentage in T₁ (6 months conservation)

The olive oil samples remain extra virgin after 6 months storage, at a temperature T °; (22-30 C °).

- 3rd analysis step:

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Fig 3: Free acidity percentage in T₂ (12 months conservation)

After 12 months storage, we observe a downgrade of 15 samples passing from the extra virgin category to virgin, presenting more than 0.8 in free acidity percentage. 15 samples were degraded from a total of 86, or 17.44% of samples.

Ethyl ester content

- 1st analysis step:

Fig 4: Ethyl esters content percentage in T₀ (0 month conservation)

All samples are extra virgin olive oils, which ethyl ester content is under the IOC standard; 30 mg / kg.

- 2nd analysis step

Fig 5: Ethyl esters content percentage in T₁ (6 months conservation)

After 6 months samples preservation, 4 samples with a high value in ethyl esters are observed which exceeds the IOC standard. A figure of 4.6% of samples was degraded after 6 months storage.

- 3rd analysis step:

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Fig 6: Ethyl esters content percentage in T₂ (12 months conservation)

After 12 months of samples storage, we observe degradation in some samples that have detected ethyl ester content above 30 mg / kg. 25 samples were degraded by a total of 86; is 29.06% degradation after one year conservation.

Appropriate ethyl ester content:

Fig 7: Ethyl esters content of all studied samples

T₀ (0 months): From the above curve, we observe that the majority of samples have ethyl ester content between 0 and 10 mg / kg.

T₁ (6 months): After 6 months conservation, we note that ethyl esters content for most analyzed samples remains in the same range [0-10] mg/Kg.

T₂ (12 months): After 12 months storage, we perceive that samples have different ethyl esters content levels, whose dominance is between [10 -30] mg/Kg.

Culture region impact on the oil quality

- *Acidity analysis:*

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Fig 8: Samples degradation percentage according to acidity analysis

(T₀= 0 month conservation; T₁= 6 months conservation; T₂=12 months conservation)

From the above curve, we observed that between T₀ and T₁ no degradation was detected. However in T₂ there was a downgrade in the three regions, where the central region had the lowest percentage that expressed on a figure of 8.33%, compared with 17.39 % in North region and Oriental region with 29.62% which marked more degradation.

- Ethyl esters content analysis:

Fig 9: Samples degradation percentage according to ethyl esters content analysis

(T₀= 0 month conservation; T₁= 6 months conservation; T₂=12 months conservation)

From the above curve, we observe a small degradation between T₀ and T₁ for oriental and central samples, when northern samples remained stable, and become higher between T₁ and T₂ so central samples are the least degraded with 13.88% compared to other regions with 37.03% and 43.47% respectively for oriental and northern samples.

DISCUSSION:

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Acidity is the main indicator of olive oils quality, it is also the oldest used in physicochemical manipulations, and this use has been mentioned in technical manuals since the XX century (Pinatell et al., 2014), it provides information on oil alteration via triglycerides hydrolysis (Meftah et al., 2014). The extra virgin olive oil quality improvement has been enhanced by alkyl esters which are an oil extrinsic compounds that synthesized in olives, and that inform a fermentation process from the harvest time (Di loreto et al., 2014 ; Lacoste, 2012), which leads to ethanol production by anaerobic metabolism of microorganisms present in poor olives quality, and methanol from the plant cell wall pectin methyl esterase (Jimenez et al., 2012). These alcohols esterify free fatty acids and produce alkyl esters. At study beginning, all analyzed samples were extra virgin olive oils with an acidity percentage less than 0.8 g of oleic acid, and the values vary between 0.20 and 0.45. The same result for ethyl esters content which has input levels within the limit set by IOC standard to know; 30 mg / Kg for extra virgin olive oil whose values are between 0 and 21, 62 mg / Kg. After 6 months storage under conditions mentioned before, we had a small increase in free acidity percentage; however, the obtained values do not exceed limits set by the IOC (0.8%), which maximum value was 0.62%, on the other hand, the ethyl ester content analysis revealed increases for some samples with a percentage of 4.6% which exceeded the COI standard, this informs about beginning of an intrinsic fermentation process, these results are similar to results obtained in other studies that found the same finding (Rabeh et al., 2018). After 12 months conservation, we notice a triglycerides hydrolysis highlighting that settles and which chemically translates as an increase in free acidity percentage for 15 samples, which maximum value is 2.1%, that gives percentage of 17.44 samples that have been downgraded from the extra virgin to virgin category (acidity percentage from 2 to 3.3: virgin olive oil according to the IOC), for ethyl ester content, we detected 29.06% samples degradation that exceeded the IOC standard up to 192.08 mg / Kg as the maximum value. Comparing degradation percentage of two studied parameters after one year storage, we found that ethyl esters analysis showed higher percentage than that of free acidity, which confirms the ethyl esters reliability and importance as a powerful marker of extra virgin olive oils quality evaluation. Based on ethyl esters level in terms of three studied regions during conservation period samples; we find that: oriental region revealed an estimated degradation of 37, 03%, 43.37% of samples were degraded in northern region, and for central region we found 13.88% of degraded samples, moreover regarding acidity it found us a decommissioning of 8.33% in center, 17.39% in the North and 29.62% in Oriental samples. Thus we find that central region is that scored the lowest degradation percentage compared to the other studied regions, whether it is in ethyl esters content or acidity, and that may be because of geographical distribution of plantation regions, whose north is characterized by poor soils, rough terrain and level rainfall of 1000 mm / year, when in the central region it has a rich and deep soil with a little uneven ground and precipitations between 450 and 500 mm / year (COI, 2012), the oriental region is a region of small olive production (Tanouti et al, 2011), and this because of climatic variance between the North (Mediterranean climate influenced by mountains) and the South (climate influenced by Saharan factors: drought, region desertification), which has repercussions on the rainfall level (400mm / year in the north and 100mm / year in the south) explaining the poor vegetation cover (RMHCPO, 2012). This observation reveals olive production importance and improvement in central region of Morocco, whose results we obtained are similar to those reported by the Ministry of Agriculture and Maritime Fisheries (TEF, 2016), who have shown great agricultural, forestry and agro-industrial potential offered by this region to the olive sector and sustainable development lever for Morocco, which is today at the heart of climate issues and major food security, and who must respond to the new requirements that fit into national and international strategies. During storage period, we observe that between T_0 and T_1 the interval of [0-10] mg / kg contains the most dominant values in ethyl esters, whereas in T_2 this value rose to the interval of [10-30] mg / kg.

Following this observation, we can estimate that ethyl esters content of extra virgin olive oil samples from the predominant variety in Moroccan orchards, namely: Moroccan picholine has an average of 17.10 mg / Kg; this value is considered lower than that set by IOC chemists (30 mg / kg), and will guarantee Moroccan oils an added value thus ensuring national olive oil production a primordial place in market and international bodies.

CONCLUSION:

The results we obtained in this study allowed us to conclude that studied conservation conditions have kept olive oil one year with a conservation percentage of up to 70%, which allows deducing that good conditioning is the key factor of success for a better oil conservation and its virtues improvement. Therefore, mode and duration storage has an impact on oil quality. Therefore, we can conclude that for the conservation of extra virgin olive oil, the olive trees of the central region of Morocco can benefit from a good storage while retaining their high nutritional quality proven by the analysis of acidity and the content of ethyl esters, which remain the most significant marker for extra virgin olive oil quality evaluation.

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